

Formulation and Evaluation of Suture from Banana Pseudo-stem Fibers

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Abstract

In this investigation, suture material was made from a banana pseudo stem. Creating a sophisticated antimicrobial-releasing suture material from banana fiber for suturing. The pseudo stem of a banana is used to create suture material, which is then degummed, braided, and coated. Suture material was loaded with the natural polymers psyllium husk and gum tragacanth and impregnated with the antibacterial medication Clindamycin phosphate. Drug-coated suture material has been discovered to have great tensile strength and to be slightly biocompatible with human erythrocytes. Because the cut pseudo stem was initially retted in water for three to four days, excellent tensile strength was attained. Clindamycin phosphate drug-loaded suture material from a pseudo stem of a banana showed a prolonged release of the drug. Sutures that have been loaded with drugs show potential physical and chemical properties that are equivalent to those of commercially available products

Keywords: Banana Suture, Pseudo-stem fiber, Clindamycin.

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Introduction

One of the most well-known and practical plants in the world is the banana. After rice, wheat, and corn, the banana is the fourth-largest agricultural food crop and is a tropical fruit that is grown all over the world. Only India contributes about 27% of the total global banana production. Maharashtra is the state that produces the most bananas in India, according to information from the National Horticulture Board for 2021–22. The banana is a member of the Musaceae family of the genus *Musa*. The fruits are parthenocarpic fruit since they lack seeds. *Musa acuminata* and *Musa balbisiana* are the two main varieties of edible bananas. [1]

One of the earliest fruits known to humankind is the banana, sometimes known as the "Apple of Paradise". The banana is a member of the Musaceae family of the genus *Musa*. The fruits are parthenocarpic fruit since they lack seeds. Bananas can be eaten and come in two main species: *Musa acuminata* and *Musa balbisiana* colla. The ripening of bananas is often ethylene-dependent. They are climacteric fruits. Following the monsoon season, that is, in October and November, banana plants are widely and heavily planted; but, with effective irrigation methods, banana plants can also be cultivated in February and March. This is the only crop that may be used as food, bedding, and roofing. The fruit can vary in size, color, and firmness, but can usually be identified by its elongated, curving shape, soft flesh that is high in starch. The most popular dessert fruit in the world, bananas are a staple starch crop for millions of people and a significant source of income for growers throughout the tropics and subtropics. [2]

The fruit banana is not only very healthy but also useful as a fragrance, beauty care product, antioxidant, and cancer prevention agent. Banana peels were once utilized by native people to hasten the healing of wounds. Banana peel and leaves have traditionally been used therapeutically, and recent evidence-based research is confirming this use. [3]

India produces 31.5 million tons of bananas annually. More biomass is produced when bananas are formed, however this biomass is wasted. People now place a great priority on protecting forests and making wise use of agricultural and forestry waste. This tendency is primarily driven and accelerated by the conflict between depleting wood resources and rising use of items made from wood fiber. Furthermore, there are other benefits to using cellulose fibers: It is inexpensive, recyclable, and environmentally friendly. [4]

Banana Fiber:

A lingo-cellulosic fiber made from banana pseudo-stems, banana fiber is one of the best fibers and has great mechanical qualities. As agricultural byproducts from banana farming, banana fiber is readily accessible.

Fig.1 Banana Pseudo-stem

Fig.2 Banana Fiber

Musa balbisiana, sometimes known as a Banana, is a fruit that is mostly grown in India, South Asia, and Southern China. With an annual production of 16 million tons, India is the world's largest producer of bananas. Banana fiber production on a large scale could make a significant contribution to the success of an industrial venture based on banana fiber. After the fruits are harvested, the pseudo-stem's waste is processed to make banana fiber, which could be used as a raw material for clothing, household items, or the production of banana paper. Mostly made of cellulose, lignin, hemicellulose, and pectin, banana fibers are light in weight and feature microfibrillar angles that improve their tensile strength. [4]

Materials and methods

Clindamycin Phosphate was provided by Oxford Laboratory, Thane, India. Dried and separated Banana fiber from Banana Pseudo stem from Farm. Psyllium Husk, Gum Tragacanth and PEG (Research-Lab Fine Chem Industries, Mumbai) was used as components of the coated Sutures. All other ingredients and reagents were of analytical grade and were used as received.

Suture Fabrication and Drug Impregnation: A banana pseudo stem was sliced and then submerged in water for three to four days. Fibers were created from sheaths after soaking in water for three to four days. Raw banana fiber was properly cleaned to eliminate any debris, allowed to air dry, and then degummed in a water bath for 30 minutes using a 2% sodium hydroxide solution. After degumming, the fiber was thoroughly washed using tap water 5–6 times, and the pH was then tested using pH paper. In addition to washing with tap water and distilled water for two or three times, the degummed fiber was also pH tested after washing. Degummed fibers must have a neutral pH. Add 1-2 drops of concentrated HCl to degummed fibers to neutralize their pH if it is alkaline. To get rid of any remaining Sodium Hydroxide, degummed fiber was washed before being dried at 37 degrees Celsius and 65% relative humidity. In addition, the degummed fiber

was braided manually using the same method that was used to make banana sutures. Prior to usage, the braided suture was further sterilized using the moist heat sterilization procedure in an autoclave at 121 degrees Celsius and 100 kilograms of pressure for 20 minutes. Different concentrations of medication gel and polymer were impregnated into the sterilized braided fiber. And to get rid of any air bubbles, that gel was placed in a sonicator for 15 minutes. A coating was applied by loosely gripping both ends of a braided fiber.

Table No.1: Formula for Drug and polymer

Chemical	Quantity (1%)	Quantity (2%)	Quantity (3%)
Psyllium Husk	0.1g	0.2g	0.3g
PEG 4000	0.1g	0.2	0.3g
PEG 600	0.1ml	0.2ml	0.3ml
Gum Tragacanth	0.1g	0.2g	0.3g
Clindamycin Phosphate	0.1g	0.1g	0.1g

A braid was created using eight degummed, sterilized fibers, each measuring 15 cm in order to keep braided fibers rough, a coating gel made of psyllium husk, PEG 4000, PEG 600 and Drug is used. Braided fibers were made somewhat smoother by adding PEG 600 to the coating gel and applying it to them. Some braided fibers got soft and some turned rough after adding an additional 0.1ml of PEG 600 to coating gel and applying it to braided fibers.

Fourier Transform Infrared Studies:

Fig.3 FTIR spectrum of Drug and polymer

An FTIR spectrum of formulation shows no any considerable change in peak of complex indicating compatibility between drug and polymer.

Evaluation Test

Tensile strength: By varying the load, it was possible to manually determine the tensile strength of commercial suture, raw banana fiber, degummed fiber, and drug coated fiber.

Table No.2: Tensile properties of different sutures made from banana pseudo-stem and the commercially available suture

Sample	Toughness (MPa)
Commercial product	2239.43
Raw Banana fiber	217.58
Degummed fiber	843.95
Drug coated fiber:	
1% coated fiber	1353.20
2% coated fiber	1360.46
3% coated fiber	1420.85

With alkali treatment and coating, the tensile characteristics of the banana fiber were enhanced. The tensile characteristics of commercially available sutures, raw banana fiber, degummed fiber, and drug-coated fiber are shown in the table. The raw, degummed, and drug-coated sutures were found to have toughness values of 217.58, 843.95 and 1353.20 MPa, respectively. The maximal toughness of the commercially available suture was 2239.43 MPa. The findings demonstrate that commercially available suture and antimicrobial drug-coated banana suture exhibit roughly comparable tensile properties. Drug-coated suture that has been impregnated in coating gel outperforms raw banana fiber in terms of tensile strength thanks to changes made to the suture's surface characteristics. Due to differences in the suture braiding process, our prepared sutures and commercially available sutures differ slightly from one another. While both the drug-coated suture and banana suture were made using a hand braiding approach, the latter was made utilizing a mechanical braiding method.

Hemocompatibility: A standard procedure was followed during a hemolysis experiment. A healthy human volunteer provided blood, which was drawn into siliconized sodium citrate tubes. Before starting the experiment, the human subject gave their informed consent, and the test was run three hours after blood was drawn. Separately incubated with 10 ml of blood (Blood and PBS in 1:9) for 1 hour at 37⁰C were the

commercial product, degummed fiber, and antibiotic medication coated suture. After one hour, the tubes were centrifuged, and a UV spectrophotometer was used to determine the optical density of the supernatant. The experiment was carried out in triplicate. The largest amount of hemolysis seen in a drug-coated banana pseudo-stem suture was 0.071%, although 5% is the allowable limit for blood-containing biomaterials. The material was impregnated with clindamycin phosphate

SEM Studies: Raw Banana Fiber

Fig.4 Raw Banana Fiber

Drug Coated Banana Fiber

Fig.5 Drug coated banana suture

The above figures show the FESEM images of dug coated pseudo-stem sutures and raw banana fiber. The surface morphology of raw banana fiber is rough and uneven (Fig.no.33). The existence of lignocellulosic components including lignin, hemicellulose, and cellulose, which are mostly made of carbon and oxygen, is what's causing the roughness, as was validated by SEM-EDX research.

***In Vitro* Drug Release**

The antibacterial medication [Clindamycin phosphate] release profile was evaluated in PBS at pH 6.3, 6.8, and 7.7, which corresponds to various skin pH values ranging from comparatively low to high pH during wound healing. Micro centrifuge tubes holding 1ml of the buffers were filled with a 10 cm suture and continuously shaken at 37 °C. An aliquot of 0.1 ml was recovered at various time intervals (24, 48, 72, 96, 120, and 144 hr.) to measure the absorbance of each sample using a UV spectrophotometer at various wavelengths (290 nm, pH 6.3, 289 nm, pH 6.8, and 287 nm, pH 7.7). PBS was simultaneously added in an equal amount to each of the micro centrifuge tubes. The ratio of the drug released over time to the amount placed onto the suture was used to calculate the release percentage.

Fig. 6 *In vitro* drug release of Clindamycin phosphate

In all of the investigated pH ranges, drug-coated suture showed a biphasic release pattern with a slow and persistent release of clindamycin phosphate for up to 144 hours. Drug release started at pH 7.7 at 24 hours and rise gradually as the incubation period lengthened. The slope of the curve attained a plateau at 81.05% after 144 hours of incubation. Additionally, the suture exhibits a similar pattern in the drug release at pH 6.3 and 6.8, where a release of 69.32% and 72.95%, respectively, was noted. The sustained drug release is facilitated by the use of the natural base materials psyllium husk and gum tragacanth as the drug loading agent. Gum Tragacanth has the capacity to keep the loaded medication in the wound region for an extended period of time. The most desirable quality for rapid wound healing is sustained release since it helps keep the wound's aseptic state for a longer period of time. According to studies, an alkaline atmosphere speeds up hydrolytic breakdown, which improves the way drugs are released. In this investigation, the same outcome was obtained by releasing the maximal amount of the medication (81.05%) at an alkaline pH of 7.7.

Antimicrobial Studies:

Antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria by Disc diffusion method

Procedure: The bacterial cultures were used to create the microorganism's inoculums. Clean, sterilized Petri plates were filled with 15 ml of nutritional agar (Hi media) medium, which was then given time to cool and harden. A spreading stick was used to evenly distribute the bacterial strain's broth across the medium until it had dried completely. The sample was placed on the plate in the appropriate manner after the agar had solidified, and the plates were then incubated for 24 hours at 37⁰C. The Zone of Inhibition (ZI) diameters were measured in order to assess the antibacterial activity.

Day 1

Day 2

Day 3

Day 4

Fig .7 Photographic Images Showing Antimicrobial Activity.

When tested with the bacterial strain *Staphylococcus aureus*, the drug-coated banana pseudo stem fiber suture exhibits Moderate antibacterial efficacy.

Conclusion

In the current work, an effort was made to create a perfect suture from leftover banana pseudo stem waste that matched the qualities of commercially available product. The produced suture has strong tensile strength, demonstrates prolonged drug release, *in vitro* testing revealed that the banana suture had moderate antibacterial efficacy against contagious microorganisms. The results of this study may also aid in the development of banana farmers by enhancing the value of agricultural trash and so minimizing environmental harm.

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